

Effects of Vocational Guidance and Counselling on Students' Choice of Career in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effects of vocational guidance and counselling on students' choice of career in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. To achieve the purpose of the study, four (4) objectives of the study, four (4) research questions and four (4) null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study made use of quasi-experimental research design. The population of the study was 11,920 senior secondary II (SSII) students of all public secondary schools in Rivers State for the 2024/2025 academic session. The sample size of one hundred and fifty students for the pre-test and the same one hundred and fifty students for the post-test. The sampling technique used was a multistage sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire that was rated using four-point rating scale. The data gathered were analyzed using weighted mean and standard deviations for the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) statistic at 0.05 level of significance. Based on the data analysis, the findings revealed that vocational guidance and counselling has positive and significant effects on career education, assessment and testing, career exploration and career development planning on career choice of students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Based on the findings of the study, the study recommends that: schools incorporate comprehensive career education programmes into their curriculum to provide students with the knowledge and skills needed to make informed decision. The Ministry of Education at the state level should provide public secondary schools with qualified career counsellors and coaches who can offer individualized guidance and support to students as they navigate their career choices.

Key words: Assessment and testing, Career, Career development, Career education, Career exploration, Guidance and Counselling, Vocational

INTRODUCTION

Vocational guidance and counselling services are essential tools in students' development especially during the adolescent stage. Adolescent stage is characterized by rapid growth and change: physically, socially, spiritually, morally and intellectually. Most adolescents are in the secondary schools, and that is why guidance and counselling services are very essential in this level of education. Bark (2013) noted that guidance and counselling is the assistance made available by qualified and trained persons to an individual of any age to help him/her to manage his/her own life activities, develop his/her own points of view, make his/her own decisions and carry his/her own burden. In addition, Braddock (2011) stated that, the purpose of guidance and counselling in schools is to improve academic achievement, foster positive study attitudes and habits, increase acquisition and application of conflict resolution skills, and decrease school dropouts. Lack of guidance and counselling in adolescence has resulted to increase in unpleasant outcomes in the society. These include school dropouts, drug abuse, crimes, and even failure to secure jobs.

Guidance and Counselling is a concept (mental idea), and a construct which is an intellectual idea consisting of the following; appraisal, information, planning, placement and follow-up, counselling, evaluation, and orientation. Counselling is a subset of guidance and a face-to-face relationship between the counsellor and the counselee. Counselling is divided into three domains namely, Educational Counselling, Vocational Counselling and Personal-Social Counselling.

Vocational Counselling assesses an individual's interests, intelligence, aptitudes, abilities and skills in order to create and follow a career path and practice a vocation. Different people have different concept of vocation. To some, vocation is a means to an end in obtaining employment that pays the bills, and to others, it is a gateway to a rewarding career. Vocational Counselling also known as career counselling involves all counselling activities associated with career planning and choices over the life span of an individual, including all aspects of the individual's needs regarding leisure, family, and work. Thomas (2020) defined career counselling as the process of helping an individual select, prepare for, enter, and function effectively in an occupation. Thomas (2020) further indicated that vocational counselling processes involve not only planning, making choices and decisions, but enables children and youth to choose and develop careers that are not only sellable, but that which can also make them to be self-employed.

Vocational counselling or career counselling is all about helping people choose the right career path with assistance in solving problems related to vocational planning and occupational choice. Every young man or woman requires advice as to what kind of work will be most suitable. When such an advice is given, it is known as vocational guidance or career guidance. From the foregoing, vocational guidance follows a process of collecting useful data comprising students' academic

achievements, obtaining vocational interest aptitude and personality test results which are used to assist the candidate in making informed choices. From the knowledge gained, the candidate will be guided as to which job is best suited for him/her. Vocational guidance is needed at the school and college level. On the basis of this guidance, the students may choose science, commerce or art subjects. Therefore, vocational counselling focuses on identifying the problems and working through them in order to ultimately resolve them. Vocational guidance assumes that some factors influence the student's choice of career such as family and societal expectations, personal interests and preferences, and exposure to different career options. As Napier (2012) comments, vocational guidance is the process by which all the various factors affecting an individual's occupational choice is sorted out, weighted and brought into focus, and by which the young person is helped to develop his/her own potentials.

Denga (2016) also defined career as the total series of roles and work experience a person occupies throughout his lifetime. Samson (2014) maintained that career is the total interest of jobs held during a worker's lifetime. This means that when we talk about ones' career, we mean the totality of varied and accumulated experiences preceding an individual's engagement in a specific job or occupation. Achebe (2013) and Ipaye (2016) stated that career is a general work description that often includes, vocation, profession and even occupation. Wrenn (2013) asserts that vocation means commitment, a sense of purpose for the total activity of one's life and the career choice is part of this larger vocational purpose for the total activity of one's life. From the foregoing, the researcher aims to investigate the "independent variable" effects of vocational guidance and counselling on the "dependent variable" students' choice of career in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State using four variables: career education, assessment and testing, career development planning.

Conceptual Review

Concept of Vocational Guidance

Since the beginning of the twentieth century vocational guidance and vocational education have had a strong inter-relationship. The relationship is based on the assumption that vocational guidance could help make wise occupational choices and that vocational education could help them prepare for what they had chosen. Parsons's early formulation of vocational guidance was the need to distribute the large number of immigrants arriving in the eastern parts of America throughout an expanding industrial structure, the original emphasis was on "matching" person and job (Bark, 2013). The operational assumptions were that individuals could be described in terms of the traits they possessed (e.g., aptitudes, skills, interests), that each occupation could be described in terms of the combinations of these traits it required, and that fitting the individual's pattern of traits to the occupation which most clearly required that specific pattern of traits would result in a meaningful and long-lasting career choice.

The National Vocational Guidance Association in 1937 adopted a definition of vocational guidance which began to broaden Parsons's model, although this was more implicit than explicit. They defined vocational guidance as "the process of assisting the individual to choose an occupation, prepare for it, enter upon it and progress in it". From this definition of vocational guidance was a concern for active and deliberate choice among occupational possibilities, considering and deciding among educational pathways to such occupational goals (including but not limited to vocational education), and receiving vocational guidance support during the period of work adjustment.

In 1951 the notions that the person needs to be helped to learn how to choose, to choose on the basis of all relevant personal characteristics, rather than simply aptitudes and performance, and that choice is a process rather than an event were really sharpened. The National Vocational Guidance Association around that time revised the definition vocational guidance. The new definition of vocational guidance, proposed by Donald Super and adopted by the Association, was "the process of helping a person to develop and accept an integrated and adequate picture of himself/herself and of his/her role in the world of work, to test this concept against reality, and to convert it into a reality, and to convert it into a reality, with satisfaction to himself/herself and benefit to society". Surely, the 1951 definition of vocational guidance shifted the emphasis of vocational guidance from the needs of the occupational structure to the needs of the individual and in the process espoused individual freedom of choice (Denga, 2016).

From the ever-widening definitions of vocational guidance the most recent twist is the substitution of the term vocation with the term career hence the recent term career guidance. Career guidance emphasizes that choices of education and of occupation are parts of a broader and lifelong pattern of interacting choices making up a career, a life-style. From his perspective, career guidance includes consideration of leisure activities, personal values, intermediate choices, distant as well as immediate, the kinds of personal themes one's choices should serve, and the development of decision-making.

Concept of Vocational Counselling

Vocational counselling is a type of counselling that focused on helping individuals explore and make informed decisions about their career paths. It involves providing guidance, support, and resources to individuals who are seeking clarification, direction, or assistance in their vocational pursuits. Vocational counsellors work with clients to assess their interests, aptitudes, values, and goals, and then help them identify suitable career options that align with their strengths and aspirations. They may use various tools and assessments to gather information about the client's skills and interests, and provide guidance on education and training necessary for specific careers, job search strategies, and career development (Ipaye, 2016). The goal of vocational counselling is

to empower individuals to make informed decisions about their career paths and find fulfilment and success in their chosen occupations.

Career Information

Career information plays a crucial role in the vocational guidance and counselling process, especially within the context of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. Providing students with accurate and comprehensive career information is essential for assisting them in making informed decisions about their future careers. Historically, the availability and dissemination of career information have significantly evolved over time. In the past, career information was primarily obtained from limited sources such as family and community members, or through observations of adults in various occupations. However, the emergence of vocational guidance and counselling services in educational institutions has broadened students' access to diverse and accurate career information (Igwe, 2018).

In public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, vocational guidance and counselling programmes have been instrumental in providing students with career information including details about the job market, educational requirements, salary expectations, and the skills needed for different careers. These activities are often facilitated through career fairs, workshops, and one-on-one counselling sessions. Research has consistently demonstrated the positive effects of career information on students' career decision-making within the context of vocational guidance and counselling. A study by Watkins and Colleagues (2017) found that when students have access to comprehensive career information, they are better able to explore various career options and make informed decisions about their future career paths.

Furthermore, career information has been shown to increase students' awareness of non-traditional career paths and opportunities in growing industries, potentially mitigating gender stereotyping in career choices (Betz, 2017). This is particularly important for public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, where students may benefit from exposure to a broader range of career possibilities. Career information also supports students in aligning their interests, skills, and aspirations with potential career paths, ultimately leading to greater job satisfaction and productivity. Access to relevant and up-to-date career information can empower students to set realistic career goals and pursue further education and training that correspond to their chosen career paths (Santos, 2016).

In conclusion, the provision of accurate and comprehensive career information within the framework of vocational guidance and counselling in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State has a significant impact on students' decision-making processes related to their future careers. Access to career information empowers students to explore various career options, make

informed decisions, and align their interests and skills with suitable career paths, leading to improved career satisfaction and success.

Concept of Choice of Career

The choice of career is a crucial decision that students are required to make as they progress through their education. Vocational guidance and counselling play a significant role in affecting students' decision-making processes regarding their choice of career. According to Betz (2017), vocational guidance and counselling provide students with the necessary information, resources, and support to help them make informed decisions about their future careers. Achebe (2013) opined that these services are instrumental in helping students understand their skills, interests, and values, which are essential factors in choosing a suitable career path. In the context of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, vocational guidance and counselling programmes have potential to positively affect students' career choices by providing them with the necessary guidance and support. Research has shown that vocational guidance and counselling programmes have a positive impact on students' career decision-making processes. A study conducted by Owan, and Nwagbara (2017) in Nigeria found that students who received vocational guidance and counselling were more likely to make informed career choices compared to those who did not receive such support. The authors also noted that students who participated in vocational guidance and counselling programmes were more satisfied with their career choices and had higher levels of career self-efficacy.

Furthermore, vocational guidance and counselling can help students explore a wide range of career options and understand the requirements and opportunities associated with different career paths. By gaining exposure to various careers and understanding the skills and qualifications necessary for different professions, students are better equipped to make informed decisions about their future. In the context of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, vocational guidance and counselling can help address the challenges students face in making career choices, such as limited access to information about different career options, lack of awareness about their own abilities and interests, and pressure from family and society (Oluchukwu, 2015). Through vocational guidance and counselling programmes, students can receive personalized support and advice to help them overcome these challenges and make informed career decisions.

In conclusion, vocational guidance and counselling play a significant role in affecting students' choice of career in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. By providing students with the necessary information, resources, and support, these programmes have the potential to positively impact students' career decision-making processes. Future research studies can further explore the specific effects of vocational guidance and counselling on students' choice of career in this context, and evaluate the effectiveness of existing programs in meeting the needs of students.

Statement of the Problem

An increasing focus has emerged on exploring the connection between occupational aspirations and career choices, particularly within the context of vocational guidance and counselling impact on students' career decisions in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State (Smith, & Johnson, 2021). From the foregoing, the importance of vocational guidance and counselling in the context of the effects of vocational guidance and counselling on students' choice of career in public secondary schools in Rivers State cannot be overstated. Vocational guidance and counselling services play a critical role in helping students navigate the complex landscape of career options and make informed decisions about their future. Vocational guidance and counselling provide students with opportunities to explore their interests, skills, and values, leading to a better understanding of their strengths and weaknesses. This self-awareness is crucial in guiding students towards careers that suit their abilities and aspirations.

In Rivers State, where students may face unique socio-economic challenges and limited access to career resources, vocational guidance and counselling play a vital role in leveling the playing field and ensuring that all students have equal opportunities to explore diverse career options and pursue their aspirations. There are related studies conducted on the effects of vocational guidance and counselling on students' choice of career in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. They examined the impact of vocational guidance and counselling on career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. The study revealed that students who received guidance and counselling services were more likely to make informed career choices aligned with their interests and abilities. Okafor and Amadi (2019) also explored how vocational guidance and counselling interventions influenced students' career aspirations and choices in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The findings revealed that effective counselling services positively influenced students' career decision-making processes. These studies provided valuable insights into the importance of vocational guidance and counselling in shaping students' career paths in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

The study on the effects of vocational guidance and counselling on students' choice of career in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State aims to address several gaps in the existing literature. These include: limited focus on specific geographic region, lack of empirical research in the area, limited exploration of student perspective, and need for comprehensive examination of career decision-making processes. By addressing these gaps, the study on the effects of vocational guidance and counselling on students' choice of career in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State aims to contribute valuable insights in the field of career development and counselling, particularly in the context of the specific challenges and opportunities present in the region.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the effects of vocational guidance and counselling on students' choice of career in public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State. The study sought to achieve the following objectives; to:

1. determine the extent to which vocational guidance and counselling affects career education in students' choice of career in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. ascertain the extent to which vocational guidance and counselling affects assessment and testing in students' choice of career in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. identify the extent to which vocational guidance and counselling affects career exploration in students' choice of career in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
4. analyse the extent to which vocational guidance and counselling affects career development planning in students' choice of career in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The study sought answers to the following questions:

1. To what extent does vocational guidance and counselling affect career education in students' choice of career in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does vocational guidance and counselling affect assessment and testing in students' career choice in public senior secondary schools of Rivers State?
3. To what extent does vocational guidance and counselling affect career exploration in students' career choice in public senior secondary schools of Rivers State?
4. To what extent does vocational guidance and counselling affect career development planning in students' choice of career in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses has been formulated and tested at 0.05 level significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of students in the three senatorial districts on the extent to which career education affects students' choice of career in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of students in the three senatorial districts on the extent to which assessment and testing affects students' choice of career in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of students in the three senatorial districts on the extent to which career exploration affects students' choice of career in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
4. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of students in the three senatorial districts on the extent to which career development planning affects students' choice of career in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Received: 03 February 2025

Revised: 12 February 2025

Accepted: 28 February 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15706304](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15706304)

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the quasi-experimental research design to find out the effect of vocational guidance and counselling on students' choice of career in Public Senior Secondary School in Rivers State. Trost (2016) observed that quasi-experimental research is a type of research design that lacks the random assignment of participants to experimental and control groups. The population of this study was 11,920 senior secondary II (SSII) students of all Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State for the 2024/2025 academic sessions. A sample is a smaller, manageable and representative portion of a larger population (Obilor, 2018). The sample of a study is a subset of the population of the study. Sampling is a process whereby a small portion of the total population is selected to represent the entire population (Eze, 2017). The multistage sampling technique was employed in the study. This study used for data collection, a self-structured questionnaire titled "Effects of Vocational Guidance and Counselling on Students' Career Choice Questionnaire (EVCSCCQ). The data collected were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) with frequency tables; weighted mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. An item is accepted if the criterion mean is above 2.50 and rejected if below 2.50. The criterion mean is obtained by adding together and dividing by 2 the scales of 1, 2, 3 and 4 representing strongly disagreed, disagreed, agreed and strongly agreed respectively. The null hypotheses were tested using the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) statistic with the use of SPSS at the 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What are the effects of career education on career choice of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on the Effects of Career Education on Career Choice of Students of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/N	Statement	Exp. Group 1			Exp. Group 2			Control Group		
		\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk	\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk	\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk
1	Helps students to develop the skills that are needed to evaluate potential career paths.	3.00	3.28	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	3.00	3.30	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.92	2.90	Post Mean < Pre-Mean
2	Equips students with fundamental knowledge necessary for their chosen profession.	2.98	3.34	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.96	3.32	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.88	2.78	Post Mean < Pre-Mean
3	Prepares students for their future workplace or career.	2.96	3.30	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.96	3.38	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.82	2.80	Post Mean < Pre-Mean
4	Provides the students with the essential required knowledge and skill set.	2.80	3.10	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.78	3.34	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.70	2.84	Post Mean > Pre-Mean
5	Gives students motivation and courage in their career choice for their future workplace.	2.98	3.24	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.98	3.40	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.88	2.92	Post Mean > Pre-Mean
Grand Mean Score		2.94	3.25	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.93	3.34	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.84	2.85	Post Mean > Pre-Mean

The information in Table 1 shows the results of a pre-test, and a post-test after participating in planned counselling sessions in the form of vocational guidance and counselling intervention programmes for the selected students in each of the six public senior secondary schools. The vocational guidance and counselling intervention programmes which involved group and individual counselling sessions, workshops, and career talks to help students make informed decisions about their career choice were made available to only Experimental Groups 1 and 2 (not made available to the Control Group). Table 1 reveals that the average post-test scores of the students for Experimental Groups 1 and 2 exceeded

their pre-test scores (items 1-5), indicating better informed decisions resulting from the intervention. This implies that students' knowledge after being exposed to the planned intervention sessions on career education resulted in better performance by students in their post-test scores compared to their pre-test scores before being exposed to the intervention sessions.

However, the Control Group has average pre-test and post-test scores that are not very different from each other and display inconsistent patterns. Items 1, 2, and 3 have average post-test scores less than the average pre-test scores, while items 4 and 5 have average post-test scores greater than the average pre-test scores. This confirms that the planned intervention sessions on career education yielded positive effects for Experimental Groups 1 and 2. The grand mean scores for experimental group 1 for pre-test and post-test are 2.94 and 3.25 respectively. For the experimental group 2, the grand mean scores are 2.84 and 3.34 respectively. For the control group, the grand mean scores for pre-test and post-test are 2.84 and 2.86 respectively. These indicates that the grand mean scores for experimental group 1 and 2 as well as control group are greater than the average mean score of 2.50, meaning that career education received by public senior secondary school students in Rivers State have positive effect on their career choice.

Research question 2: What are the effects of assessment and testing on career choice of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on the Effects of Assessment and Testing on Career Choice of Students of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/No.	Statement	Exp. Group 1			Exp. Group 2			Control Group		
		\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk	\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk	\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk
6	Enhance the students' opportunity to learn about themselves in making career choice.	3.00	3.26	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.96	3.32	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.88	2.86	Post Mean < Pre-Mean
7	Give students information about their strengths and ability to make career choice.	2.88	3.38	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.84	3.40	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.80	2.78	Post Mean < Pre-Mean
8	Enhance students' opportunity to know about their challenges in career choice.	2.96	3.36	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.94	3.38	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.72	2.74	Post Mean > Pre-Mean
9	Enlighten the students to know the area of	2.98	3.28	Post Mean	2.92	3.42	Post Mean	2.64	2.70	Post Mean

	their interest in making career choice.			> Pre-Mean			> Pre-Mean			> Pre-Mean
10	Help the students in the activities that promote growth and wellness in their career choice.	3.10	3.32	Post Mean	2.96	3.36	Post Mean	2.86	2.86	Post Mean
				> Pre-Mean			> Pre-Mean			= Pre-Mean
	Grand Mean Score	2.98	3.32	Post Mean	2.92	3.38	Post Mean	2.78	2.79	Post Mean
				> Pre-Mean			> Pre-Mean			> Pre-Mean

The information in Table 2 shows the results of a pre-test, and a post-test after participating in planned counselling sessions in the form of vocational guidance and counselling intervention programmes for the selected students in each of the six public senior secondary schools. The vocational guidance and counselling intervention programmes which involved group and individual counselling sessions, workshops, and career talks to help students make informed decisions about their career choice were made available to only Experimental Groups 1 and 2 (not made available to the Control Group). Table 2 reveals that the average post-test scores of the students for Experimental Groups 1 and 2 exceeded their pre-test scores (items 6 - 10), indicating better-informed decisions resulting from the intervention. This implies that students' knowledge after being exposed to the planned intervention sessions on assessment and testing resulted in better performance by students in their posttest scores compared to their pre-test scores before being exposed to the intervention sessions.

However, the Control Group has average pre-test and post-test scores that are not very different from each other and display inconsistent patterns. Items 6 and 7 have average post-test scores less than the average pre-test scores, items 8 and 9 have average post-test scores greater than the average pre-test scores, and item 10 has an average post-test score equal to the average pre-test score. This confirms that the planned intervention sessions on assessment and testing yielded positive effects for Experimental Groups 1 and 2. The grand mean scores for experimental group 1 for pre-test and post-test are 2.98 and 3.32 respectively. For the experimental group 2, the grand mean scores are 2.92 and 3.38 respectively. For the control group, the grand mean scores for pre-test and post-test are 2.78 and 2.79 respectively. These indicates that the grand mean scores for experimental group 1 and 2 as well as control group are greater than the average mean score of 2.50, meaning that assessment and testing received by public senior secondary school students in Rivers State have positive effect on their career choice.

Research Question 3: What are the effects of career exploration on career choice of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics on the Effects of Career Exploration on Career Choice of Students of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/No.	Statement	Exp. Group 1			Exp. Group 2			Control Group		
		\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk	\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk	\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk
11	Helps the students to find their desired career in school.	2.84	3.30	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.84	3.30	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.80	2.86	Post Mean > Pre-Mean
12	Guides the students in making positive career choices in school.	2.88	3.48	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.88	3.32	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.88	2.84	Post Mean < Pre-Mean
13	Empowers the student to be well-informed educationally mainly in the area of career choice	2.98	3.36	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	3.00	3.34	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.82	2.82	Post Mean = Pre-Mean
14	Informs the students in career decisions and occupational choice in society.	2.96	3.28	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	3.02	3.40	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.78	2.80	Post Mean > Pre-Mean
15	Involves the students in their research career options and their set goals.	3.00	3.34	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	3.00	3.38	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.90	2.84	Post Mean < Pre-Mean
Grand mean Score		2.93	3.35	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.95	3.35	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.84	2.83	Post Mean > Pre-Mean

The information in Table 3 shows the results of a pre-test, and a post-test after participating in planned counselling sessions in the form of vocational guidance and counselling intervention programmes for the selected students in each of the six public senior secondary schools. The vocational guidance and counselling intervention programmes which involved group and individual counselling sessions, workshops, and career talks to help students make informed decisions about their career choice were made available to only Experimental Groups 1 and 2 (not made available to the Control Group). Table 3 reveals that the average post-test scores of the students for Experimental Groups 1 and 2 exceeded their pre-test scores (items 11 - 15), indicating better-informed decisions resulting from the intervention. This implies that students' knowledge after being exposed to the planned intervention sessions on career exploration resulted in better performance by students in their post-test scores compared to their pre-test scores before being exposed to the intervention sessions.

However, the Control Group has average pre-test and post-test scores that are not very different from each other and display inconsistent patterns. Items 11 and 14 have average post-test scores greater than the average pre-test scores, items 12 and 15 have average post-test scores less than the average pre-test scores, and item 13 has an average post-test score equal to the average pre-test score. This confirms that the planned intervention sessions on career exploration yielded positive effects for Experimental Groups 1 and 2. The grand mean scores for experimental group 1 for pre-test and post-test are 2.93 and 3.35 respectively. For the experimental group 2, the grand mean scores are 2.95 and 3.35 respectively. For the control group, the grand mean scores for pre-test and post-test are 2.84 and 2.83 respectively. These indicates that the grand mean scores for experimental group 1 and 2 as well as control group are greater than the average mean score of 2.50, meaning that assessment and testing received by public senior secondary school students in Rivers State have positive effect on their career choice.

Research Question 4: What are the effects of career development planning on career choice of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics on the Effects of Career Development Planning on Career Choice of Students of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/No.	Statement	Exp. Group 1			Exp. Group 2			Control Group		
		\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk	\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk	\bar{X}_{Pre}	\bar{X}_{Post}	Rmk
16	Provides the students with a clear sense of direction in their professional lives.	2.86	3.26	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.84	3.34	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.84	2.84	Post Mean = Pre-Mean
17	Assists the students in identifying their passions in school.	2.92	3.30	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.90	3.32	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.72	2.78	Post Mean > Pre-Mean
18	Points the students in the direction of identifying their strengths and weaknesses.	3.02	3.28	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	3.02	3.36	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.88	2.90	Post Mean > Pre-Mean
19	Promotes the students to choose a career that aligns with their values and aspirations.	3.00	3.20	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	3.00	3.38	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.78	2.74	Post Mean < Pre-Mean

20	Allows the students to have self-awareness and self-development in their career choice.	2.96	3.24	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.98	3.42	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.82	2.86	Post Mean > Pre-Mean
	Grand Mean Score	2.95	3.26	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.95	3.36	Post Mean > Pre-Mean	2.81	2.82	Post Mean > Pre-Mean

The information in Table 4 shows the results of a pre-test, and a post-test after participating in planned counselling sessions in the form of vocational guidance and counselling intervention programmes for the selected students in each of the six public senior secondary schools. The vocational guidance and counselling intervention programmes which involved group and individual counselling sessions, workshops, and career talks to help students make informed decisions about their career choice were made available to only Experimental Groups 1 and 2 (not made available to the Control Group). Table 4 reveals that the average post-test scores of the students for Experimental Groups 1 and 2 exceeded their pre-test scores (items 16 - 20), indicating better-informed decisions resulting from the intervention. This implies that students' knowledge after being exposed to the planned intervention sessions on career development planning resulted in better performance by students in their post-test scores compared to their pre-test scores before being exposed to the intervention sessions.

However, the Control Group has average pre-test and post-test scores that are not very different from each other and display inconsistent patterns. Item 16 has an average post-test score equal to the average pre-test score, items 17, 18, and 20 have average post-test scores greater than average pre-test scores, and item 20 has an average post-test score less than average pre-test score. This confirms that the planned intervention sessions on career development planning yielded positive effects for Experimental Groups 1 and 2. The grand mean scores for experimental group 1 for pre-test and post-test are 2.95 and 3.26 respectively. For the experimental group 2, the grand mean scores are 2.95 and 3.36 respectively. For the control group, the grand mean scores for pre-test and post-test are 2.81 and 2.82 respectively. These indicates that the grand mean scores for experimental group 1 and 2 as well as control group are greater than the average mean score of 2.50, meaning that career development planning received by public senior secondary school students in Rivers State have positive effect on their career choice.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant effect of career education on career choice of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4.5: Analysis of Covariance of Effect of Career Education on Career Choice of Students of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	8.475 ^a	3	2.825	77.821	.000	.615
Intercept	1.173	1	1.173	32.314	.000	.181
VAR00001	1.434	1	1.434	39.514	.000	.213
VAR00003	5.105	2	2.553	70.316	.000	.491
Error	5.300	146	.036			
Total	1501.520	150				
Corrected Total	13.775					

The results in Table 4.5 show that between groups (VAR00003) has type III sum of squares = 5.105, $df = 2$, mean square = 2.553, and $F = 70.316$ that is significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant effect of career education on career choices of students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State” is rejected as $F(2, 146) = 70.316, p = 0.00 < \alpha = 0.05$. In other words, there is statistically significant effect of career education on career choice of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State because $F(2, 146) = 70.316; \alpha = 0.05 > p = 0.000$.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant effect of assessment and testing on career choice of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4.6: Analysis of Covariance of Effect of Assessment and Testing on Career Choice of Students of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	10.763 ^a	3	3.588	120.875	.000	.713
Intercept	4.555	1	4.555	153.473	.000	.512
VAR00001	.231	1	.231	7.776	.006	.051
VAR00003	8.045	2	4.023	135.533	.000	.650
Error	4.333	146	.030			
Total	1514.200	150				
Corrected Total	15.096	149				

The information in Table 4.6 shows that between groups (VAR00003) has type III sum of squares = 8.045, df = 2, mean square = 4.023, and F = 135.533 that is significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant effect of assessment and testing on career choices of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State” is rejected as $F(2, 146) = 135.533, p = 0.00 < \alpha = 0.05$. In other words, there is statistically significant effect of assessment and testing on career choice of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State because $F(2, 146) = 70.316; \alpha = 0.05 > p = 0.000$.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant effect of career exploration on career choice of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4.7: Analysis of Covariance of Effect of Career Exploration on Career Choice of Students of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	9.791 ^a	3	3.264	105.842	.000	.685
Intercept	4.507	1	4.507	146.163	.000	.500
VAR00001	.428	1	.428	13.865	.000	.087
VAR00003	8.003	2	4.002	129.768	.000	.640
Error	4.502	146	.031			
Total	1524.800	150				
Corrected Total	14.293	149				

The information in Table 4.7 shows that between groups (VAR00003) has type III sum of squares = 8.003, $df = 2$, mean square = 4.002, and $F = 129.768$ that is significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant effect of career exploration on career choices of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State” is rejected as $F(2, 146) = 129.768$, $p = 0.00 < \alpha = 0.05$. In other words, there is statistically significant effect of career exploration on career choice of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State because $F(2, 146) = 129.768$; $\alpha = 0.05 > p = 0.000$.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant effect of career development planning on career choice of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4.8: Analysis of Covariance of Effect of Career Development Planning on Career Choice of Students of Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Source		df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	8.717 ^a	3	2.906	90.693	.000	.651
Intercept	2.486	1	2.486	77.598	.000	.347
VAR00001	.552	1	.552	17.231	.000	.106
VAR00003	5.853	2	2.927	91.345	.000	.556
Error	4.678	146	.032			
Total	1499.880	150				
Corrected Total	13.394	149				

The results in Table 4.8 show that between groups (VAR00003) has type III sum of squares = 5.853, $df = 2$, mean square = 2.927, and $F = 91.345$ that is significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant effect of career development planning on career choice of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State” is rejected as $F(2, 146) = 129.768$, $p = 0.00 < \alpha = 0.05$. In other words, there is statistically significant effect of career development planning on career choice of students of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State because $F(2, 146) = 129.768$; $\alpha = 0.05 > p = 0.000$.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study on research question 1, revealed that there are significant effects of career education on career choice of students in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State. This finding is in collaboration with Denga (2016) study titled “Impact of vocational guidance and counselling on students’ academic performance in University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State”. The

study revealed that there is a positive impact of vocational guidance and counselling coaching students' academic performance in Rivers State. While the finding of the study in research question 2 revealed that there are significant effects of assessment and testing on career choice of students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. In the same vein Igwe (2018) observed that there is a significant relationship between assessment and testing and students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The relationship between assessment and testing and students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, as well as the effects of vocational guidance and counselling on students' choice of career, highlights the importance of implementing comprehensive and effective assessment and counselling practices to support students' academic and career development.

The finding of research question 3 reveals that there are significant effects of career exploration on career choice of students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The findings are correlation with Samson (2016) who observed that vocational counselling, career counselling, and personal-social counselling have positive influence on students' career aspiration in Abia State. The relationship between the influence of guidance and counselling on students' career aspirations in Abia State and the effects of vocational guidance and counselling on students' choice of career in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, concerning career exploration, emphasizes the significance of providing students with the necessary support and resources to explore and navigate their career options effectively. The finding of research question 4 revealed that there are significant effects of career development planning on career choice of students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The findings are in the same vein with Santo (2016) titled "Comparative Analysis of Factors Influencing Career Choice among Senior Secondary School Students in Rivers State, Nigeria", revealed that there were significant differences in the career preferences when grouped according to the sex, parity, parental influence and socio-economic background of the participants decisions to pursue a post-secondary degree.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the research concluded that there is a positive and significant effects of vocational guidance and counselling on career development planning and coaching to help students have higher level of preparedness for the job market. Students who have received this guidance are more likely to have the skills and knowledge needed to succeed in their chosen field, increasing their chances of finding fulfilling employment. Evidence from the study still revealed that students who have received vocational guidance and counselling are more likely to be satisfied with their chosen career path. Vocational guidance and counselling programmes often include career assessment and testing to help students understand their strengths and interests. Students who have received vocational guidance and counselling are more likely to explore a wider range of career options and choose a career that is aligned with their interests and values. The

students are most likely to have the skills and knowledge needed to succeed in their chosen field, increasing their chances of finding fulfilling employment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Schools should incorporate comprehensive career education programmes focusing on career exploration, goal settings, and decision-making skills into their curriculum to provide students with the knowledge and skills needed to make informed career decisions.
2. Schools should utilize career assessments and testing tools to help students identify their interests, skills, and values. These assessments can provide valuable insights into potential career paths and help students make informed decisions about their future.
3. Schools should provide students with opportunities for hands-on career exploration, such as job shadowing, internships, and career fairs. These experiences can help students gain a better understanding of various career options and make more informed decisions about their future.
4. Schools should help students develop personalized career development plans that outline their goals, interests, and action steps for achieving their career aspirations. These plans should be regularly reviewed and updated to ensure students are on track to meet their career.

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